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Research Article

**DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTERIZATION OF
GENTAMICIN TRANSFEROSOMAL GEL****CH. Kantlam^{1*}, CH. Suchitra², Shivani Nakirakanti³, Keerthi Nakka³,
Nischal Aponaganti³, Nithin Palle³, Qursheedunisa Begum³.**¹Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, Brilliant College of Pharmacy, Abdullapurmet Village, Hayathnagar, Rangareddy, Telangana²Assistant Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, Brilliant College of Pharmacy, Abdullapurmet Village, Hayathnagar, Rangareddy, Telangana³Department of Pharmaceutics, Brilliant College of Pharmacy, Abdullapurmet Village, Hayathnagar, Rangareddy, Telangana**Abstract:**

The present study was focused on develop and evaluate Gentamicin containing transferosomes formulation for in vitro studies. Transferosomes formulations were prepared by using thin film hydration method and were evaluated for in vitro characteristics, stability studies. Transferosomes formulation displayed highest entrapment efficiency with desired particle size. SEM analyses showed that Transferosomes formulation was spherical in shape. Transferosomes containing lipid higher percentage of drug release after 12 h as compared to other formulations. F8 formulation was found to be stable at the end of the study on storage condition. The present study suggested that Transferosomes gel formulations provide sustained and prolonged delivery of drug with enhance bioavailability.

Keywords: *Transferosomes, Gentamicin, bioavailability, thin film hydration method, In vitro drug release studies.*

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1.INTRODUCTION:

The Pharmaceutical Industry worldwide caters to the specific health needs of the patients suffering from various diseases by designing and supplying suitable dosage forms which are popularly called as Formulations in the parlance of the Pharmacists¹. An urge for preparing specialized drug delivery systems as emanated in order to enhance Bioavailability and deliver the drugs at the desired specific sites of the human body. Transdermal drug delivery systems are defined as self-contained, discrete dosage forms which, when applied to the intact skin, deliver the drug, through the skin, at a controlled rate to the systemic circulation.² At present, the most common form of delivery of drugs is the oral route. While this has the notable advantage of easy administration, it also has significant drawbacks namely poor bioavailability due to hepatic first pass metabolism and the tendency to produce rapid blood level spikes (both high and low), leading to a need for high and/or frequent dosing, which can be both cost prohibitive and inconvenient.³ To overcome these difficulties there is a need for the development of new drug delivery system; which will improve the therapeutic efficacy and safety of drugs by more precise (i.e. site specific), spatial and temporal placement within the body thereby reducing both the size and number of doses.⁴ New drug delivery system are also essential for the delivery of novel, genetically engineered pharmaceuticals (i.e. peptides, proteins) to their site of action, without incurring significant immunogenicity or biological inactivation. Apart from these advantages the pharmaceutical companies recognize the possibility of repatting successful drugs by applying the concepts and techniques of controlled drug delivery system coupled with the increased expense in bringing new drug moiety to the market⁵. One of the methods most often utilized has been transdermal delivery - meaning transport of therapeutic substances through the skin for systemic effect. Closely related is percutaneous delivery, which is transport into target tissues, with an attempt to avoid systemic effects.⁶ The present study was focused on develop and evaluate Gentamicin containing transfersomes formulation for in vitro studies. Transfersomes formulations were prepared by using thin film hydration method and were evaluated for in vitro characteristics, stability studies.

Drug excipient compatibility studies⁷

Drug excipients compatibility studies were performed to know the compatibility of excipient with drug at accelerated conditions. The study was conducted by preparing homogenous mixture of excipients with drug and filled in HDPE bags and LDPE bags. Glass vials were exposed to 600 C and 400C/75 %RH for 4 weeks and LDPE bags were exposed to 400C±75 %RH for 4 weeks. Samples were observed periodically for any physical change

2.MATERIALS AND METHODS:

2.MATERIALS AND METHODS

Gentamycin was collected as a gift sample from Hetero labs, Hyderabad and various excipients and polymers were purchased from AR chemicals, Hyderabad.

2.1 METHODOLOGY:

Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy⁸:

Fourier transform IR spectra were obtained on Shimadzu FT-IR spectrometer. Samples were prepared in KBr disks (2mg sample in 200mg KBr). The scanning range was 450-4000 cm⁻¹ and the resolution was 4 cm⁻¹.

Formulation development

Table-1: Formulation table

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4
Gentamicin	5	5	5	5
Soya lecithin	50	100	150	200
Cholesterol	50	50	50	50
Span 80	2	2	2	5
Chloroform	3	3	3	3
Methanol	1	1	1	1
Carbopol 940	250	500	750	1000

Preparation method trasferosomes

A thin-film hydration technique was employed to form transfersomes. Specific amounts of lipids were dissolved in a mixture of organic solvents consisting of methanol and chloroform (1:3) in a dry round-bottom flask. The evaporation of organic solvents was performed under vacuum using a rota evaporator at 100 rpm, at 48-50 °C. The thin lipid film thus obtained was then hydrated using water containing surfactant and drug by rotation for 1 hour at 50 °C. Each formulation was placed in an ultrasonicator bath at 150 W for 20 seconds. A dialysis bag was used to remove the free drug, and the final formulation was stored at 4 °C for further use. Blank transfersomes were prepared using the same method for each formulation⁹.

Preparation of topical transfersome gel¹⁰:

As a vehicle for incorporation of transfersomes for topical delivery, carbopol gels were prepared. Transfersomes aqueous dispersion was utilized for the formulation of topical gel. Gel polymer such as carbopol 940 was utilized to prepare transfersome gel. Various quantity of carbopol- 940 powder was dispersed into vigorously stirred (stirred by magnetic stirrer Remi 5MLH) distilled water (taking care to avoid the formation of in dispersible lumps) and allowed to hydrate for 24 hrs. The dispersion was neutralized with tri ethanolamine to adjust the pH 7.4 by using pH meter (Lab India Sab 5000).

Characterization^{10,11,12}**Vesicle size**

Transfersomes vesicles can be visualized by SEM and optical microscope. The Morphological characterization of transfersome vesicle such as shape and surface feature were projected by using optical microscope and SEM.

SEM Analysis

The shape, surface characteristics, and size of the Transfersomal gel were observed by scanning electron microscopy. Once again, 0.2 g of the Transfersomal gel in a glass tube was diluted with 10 ml of pH 7.4 phosphate buffer. The Transfersomal gel were mounted on an aluminium stub using double-sided adhesive carbon tape. Then the vesicles were sputter-coated with gold palladium (Au/Pd) using a vacuum evaporator (Edwards) and examined using a scanning electron microscope (Hitachi 3700N, Germany) equipped with a digital camera, at 10 kV accelerating voltage.

Determination of pH:

The value of pH of topical Transfersomal gel was measured by using digital pH meter (Lab India Sab 5000 pH meter) at the room temperature.

Determination of entrapment efficiency percentage:

The amount of Gentamicin entrapped in transfersomal gel was estimated by centrifugation method. 1gm of Transfersomal gel was taken and diluted with 10ml phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). This suspension was sonicated using bath sonicator for 20 minutes. Later this solution was placed in centrifugation tube and centrifuged at 14000 rpm for 30 minutes. 0.5ml of supernatant was withdrawn and diluted before going for absorbance measurement using UV spectrophotometer (UV-2960 Lab India). This gives us the total amount of untrapped drug. Entrapment efficiency is expressed as the percent of drug trapped.

$$\% \text{ Entrapment} = \frac{\text{Total drug} - \text{Diffused drug}}{\text{Total drug}} \times 100$$

In-vitro drug release studies

Modified Franz diffusion cell with a receiver compartment volume of 18ml and effective diffusion area of 2cm² was used for this study. *In-vitro* drug study was performed by using egg membrane in phosphate buffer solution (pH 7.4). To perform *in-vitro* drug release study, egg membrane was mounted horizontally on the receptor compartment of Franz diffusion cell. The effective permeation area of donor compartment exposed to receptor compartment was 2cm² and capacity of receptor compartment was 30ml. The receptor compartment was filled with 30ml of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) maintained at 37± 0.5°C and stirred by a magnetic bar at 100rpm. Transfersomal gel formulation equivalent to 80mg drug was placed on the cellophane membrane and the top of the diffusion cell was covered. At appropriate time intervals 5 ml aliquots of the receptor medium were withdrawn and immediately replaced by an equal volume of fresh phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) to maintain sink conditions. The samples were analyzed spectrophotometrically at λ max 296 nm.

Stability Studies of transfersomal gel¹³

After measuring the initial percentage entrapment of the drug in the optimized formulation, the three batches of the same formulation were stored in sealed glass ampoules (one each) at refrigeration temperature (4±2°C), room temperature (25±2°C) and body temperature (37±2°C) for a period of at least 3 months. The percentage entrapment of the drug and % drug content was determined in the formulations after 15, 30, 45 and 90 days to know the amount of drug leaked out. The percent drug lost was calculated taking the initial entrapment of drug as 100%.

3.RESULTS & DISCUSSION:**FT-IR Spectrum of Gentamicin**

FT-IR Spectra of Gentamicin and F3 formulation were recorded. All these peaks have appeared in formulation and physical mixture, indicating no chemical interaction between drug and excipients.

Fig-1: FTIR Studies of Gentamicin

Fig-2: FTIR Studies of physical mixture of drug and excipients

FTIR spectra of drug in KBr pellets at moderate scanning speed by 4000–400 cm^{-1} was made. Compatibility studies were performed using IR spectrophotometer. The IR spectrum of Pure drug and physical mixture of drug and excipients were studied. The characteristic absorption of peaks were obtained as above and as they were in official limits ($\pm 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) the drug is compatible with excipients.

Particle size of Transfersomes

Fig-3: Particle size of Optimized formulation

The mean particle size of optimized transfersomes was found to be 112 nm

pH value of topical transfersome gel:

The value of pH of topical transfersome gels was measured by using digital pH meter (Labindia Sab 5000 pH meter) at the room temperature. The pH of all topical transfersomal gels were found to be in the range of 6.5 to 7.2.

Table-2: pH value of topical transfersome gel

F. No	pH
F1	6.5
F2	7.2
F3	6.6
F4	6.8

SEM Analysis

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) SEM revealed that the Gentamicin transfersomes were smooth and spherical without any aggregation.

Fig-4: SEM Analysis of Transfersomal gel

Entrapment efficiency

Table-3: Percentage entrapment efficiency

F. No	% EE
F1	79.63
F2	81.23
F3	85.39
F4	84.20

In vitro drug release studies

The diffusion medium used was phosphate buffer solution pH 7.4. In the Franz diffusion cell, the Dialysis membrane was mounted between donor and receptor compartment of diffusion cell. Egg membrane separated both the compartments. Area of membrane separating two compartments was 1.7662 cm². Transfersomal gel (20 ml) volume was accurately pipetted into donor compartment which was then covered with aluminum foil to avoid any

evaporation. Diffusion medium (20 ml) was maintained at 37 ± 1 °C, so that the membrane just touches the receptor medium surface. A magnetic bar continuously stirred in the diffusion medium at 100 rpm. Each of 1 ml volume was withdrawn at required time intervals and replaced by 1 ml volume of receptor medium (phosphate buffer pH 7.4) to maintain the sink condition. These samples were analyzed by UV spectrophotometer at maximum wavelength 296 nm.

Table-4: Diffusion studies of Transfersomal gel

Time	F1	F2	F3	F4
0	0	0	0	0
1	17.19	16.42	18.12	16.93
2	27.10	24.60	26.39	27.46
3	35.13	32.99	38.56	36.82
4	45.32	55.37	56.83	55.34
6	56.35	65.10	67.89	68.19
8	78.10	77.52	78.15	75.13
10	83.69	84.56	85.93	84.23
12	94.50	95.69	96.38	93.52

Fig-5: Diffusion studies of Transfersomes (F1-F4)

Stability studies:

There was no significant change in physical and chemical properties of the nanoparticle's formulation F3 after 3 months. Parameters quantified at various time intervals were shown.

Table-5: Results of stability studies of optimized formulation F-3

F. Code	Parameters	Initial	1 st Month	2 nd Month	3 rd Month	Limits as per Specifications
F-3	25 ^o C/60%RH % Release	96.38	95.57	94.60	93.55	Not less than 85 %
F-3	30 ^o C/75% RH % Release	96.38	94.69	94.57	93.50	Not less than 85 %
F-3	40 ^o C/75% RH % Release	96.38	94.25	94.16	93.12	Not less than 85 %

4.CONCLUSION:

The work was carried out to prepare Gentamicin transfersomal gel to achieve controlled release effect at site of administration

- The pre-formulation studies like UV analysis of Indomethecin, FTIR were complied with BP standards. The FTIR spectra revealed that there was no interaction between the drug and excipients.
- Transfersome formulations were prepared by thin film hydration technique and were incorporated into polymeric gel. The Formulation F3 containing Lecithin: Span 80 has higher entrapment efficiency and maximum drug release.
- In-vitro drug release studies showed that, transfersome gels were found to increase the permeation and deposition showing a controlled effect.
- Stability studies performed for optimized transfersome gel formulations indicates that prepared transfersomal gel have more

stability at freezing temperature than that of room temperature.

- Based on the above data, it was confirmed that prepared Indomethecin transfersomal gel (F3) can be considered as one of the promising approach to reduce the dosing frequency and to maintain drug concentration at the desired site for longer time.

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